

ISic3182

I.Sicily inscription 3182

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329574

1. Ἰωάννης.
2. τόπος.
3. C □ Ω ²⁶Χριστὸς Σωτήρ²⁶.
- 4.

Edition: PHI329575

1. Ἰωάννης
2. τόπος.
3. [A] □ Ω
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645512
PHI 329574
PHI 329575

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0007

Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At no.6

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3182. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388282>